

FLUIDITY AND FREE VOLUME IN LIQUIDS

BY ASOKE KUMAR MUKHERJEE

The fluidity of a liquid has been taken to be a function of its free volume. The nature of the function has been worked out and a linear relation has been established for ordinary conditions of temperature and pressure. The nature of the relationship at other conditions has also been indicated.

The concept of the existence of free volume in a liquid is not a new one, because since the time of McLeod (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, 21, 151) different workers, like Eyring ("The Theory of Rate Processes", 1940), Lennard-Jones and Devonshire (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1937, A, 163, 53) and Kirkwood (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, 18, 380) have made use of this concept to explain some of the properties of liquids.

A liquid has been considered here to be a highly condensed gas, the molecules being squeezed together by their mutual interaction (by Van der Waal's force or otherwise). In this manner it is possible to treat liquids by the help of equations used for gases provided that we use free volume instead of total volume inhabited by a gaseous molecule and that we introduce necessary corrections for the attraction between liquid molecules.

This idea of free volume was first advanced by Eyring (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, 4, 283) in a slightly different manner, but he did not take this into full account in his treatment of viscous flow of liquids. In the present investigation this idea has been amplified, extended and utilised in treating viscous flow of liquids, in general, under varying conditions of different physical factors.

Moreover, the concept of free volume assumed herein differs from Eyring's "Hole theory" in another respect. He assumes that the effect of temperature is to increase the number of holes in the liquid. This in effect regards the free volume as discontinuous; whenever there is any increase or decrease of free volume in a liquid, it occurs by the introduction or disappearance of holes which have a definite size compared to that of the molecules. In the present investigation, free volume has been regarded as continuous, so that the differential relations may be used freely in all calculations.

In the present paper our point of interest is to ascertain how the fluidity of a liquid is related to free volume.

From what has been stated above, the fluidity is certainly dependent on free volume, *i.e.*,

$$\phi = \psi(V_f)$$

where ϕ is the fluidity and ψ represents a function of the free volume, V_f . Assuming this to be an 'n'th order function of V_f ,

$$\phi = A_0 + AV_f^n$$

where A_0 and A are constants. According to the definition of free volume, as proposed herein, when V_f is zero, the liquid loses its fluidity, *i.e.*,

$\phi = 0$ when $V_f = 0$, whence,

$$A_0 = 0$$

So that,

$$\phi = AV_f^n \quad \dots (1)$$

To determine the exact order of the function the following procedure was adopted. Eyring and Kincaid (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, 6, 620) have derived the relation connecting free volume with the velocity of longitudinal waves of the form

$$U = (v/V_f)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{RT\gamma}{M}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where U is the velocity of any longitudinal wave in the liquid; v , the total volume inhabited by a liquid molecule; γ , the ratio of specific heats; M , the molecular weight; R , the gas constant, and T , the absolute temperature.

Now from equation (1), we have

$$V_f = (\phi/A)^{1/n} = (\phi/A)^x \quad \text{where } x = 1/n$$

whence

$$\begin{aligned} U &= (A/\phi)^{\frac{x}{2}} \cdot v^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{RT\gamma}{M}} \\ &= (A/\phi)^{\frac{x}{2}} (M/N\rho)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{RT\gamma}{M}} \end{aligned}$$

where N is the Avogadro's number and ρ , the density of the liquid.

$$\text{Or,} \quad U = BT^{\frac{1}{2}}/\phi^{x/2} \cdot \rho^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (3)$$

where B is a constant for the liquid and equals

$$A^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot M^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot R^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}} / N^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot M^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Thus, knowing the value of U for two different temperatures, and the corresponding values of fluidity and density, we can determine the value x :

$$\log U = \log B + \frac{1}{2} \log T - \frac{x}{2} \log \phi - \frac{1}{2} \log \rho$$

$$\text{whence } x = \frac{(\log U_1 + \frac{1}{2} \log \rho_1 - \frac{1}{2} \log T_1) - (\log U_2 + \frac{1}{2} \log \rho_2 - \frac{1}{2} \log T_2)}{\frac{1}{2} (\log \phi_2 - \log \phi_1)} \quad \dots (4)$$

This formula (4) has been tried on ten liquids. The values of U for these were taken from the data for the velocity of ultrasonic waves in these liquids (Lagemann, McMillan and Woolf, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1949, 17, 369; Lagemann, McMillan (Jr.) and Woolsey, *ibid.*, 1948, 16, 247; Pellam and Galt, *ibid.*, 1946, 14, 608), data for fluidity and density being obtained from the Landolt Borustein Tabellen. The values of 'x' were calculated and thence the value n , its reciprocal, as shown in the table below. The range of temperature through which the liquids have been studied are also given in the table.

TABLE I

Liquids.	Range of temp.	Mean ' π '.
Carbon tetrachloride	0°-40°	1.00
Benzene	10°-40°	0.89
Chlorobenzene	10°-30°	0.86
<i>s</i> -Tetrachloroethane	10°-30°	1.12
Bromobenzene	0°-40°	1.01
Fluorobenzene	20°-30°	0.80
1-Nonene	10°-30°	0.80
1-Decene	10°-30°	0.96
1-Undecene	10°-30°	1.00
1-Tridecene	10°-30°	1.20

The results in the table show that the values of π are in all the cases approximately equal to unity within a temperature range of 0° to 50° on the average. The relation between fluidity and free volume in a liquid thus comes out to be (from equation 1) a linear relation

$$\phi = AV_f \quad \dots (5)$$

which is of the same form as proposed by McLeod (*loc. cit.*) in the case of free space as enunciated by him.

In the above derivation, there appears a constant B which is a function of M , the molecular weight. So it is expected that the linear relationship will hold so long as M remains constant. If, however, under any condition M changes due to association or dissociation of molecules, the constancy of B will no longer be maintained and the value of ' π ' is likely to differ from unity. So far as the ordinary temperature and pressure are concerned, it is evident from the data presented above that a linear relationship exists between ϕ and V_f . At sufficiently higher or lower temperature, where there is likelihood of dissociation or association, the equation should be used with caution. Similarly at higher pressures where the molecules (at least in some cases) are known to associate, the value of ' π ' should not justifiably be assumed to be unity. Therefore it is only when V_f changes with temperature within the range specified above that the value of ' π ' may be taken to be unity. This conclusion is very useful as will be shown in our subsequent discussion appearing in future communications.

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